

EMG Data Augmentation for Grasp Classification Using Generative Adversarial Networks

V. Mendez*, C. Lhoste*, S. Micera, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—Electromyography (EMG) has been used as an interface for the control of robotic hands for decades but with the improvement of embedded electronics and decoding algorithms, many applications are now envisaged by companies. Deep learning has shown the possibility to increase decoding performance but it requires large amounts of data to show its full capabilities. However, recording such amounts of EMG signals face several issues since recording hours of data from patients is very time-consuming and can result in muscle fatigue. We explore a deep learning data augmentation strategy using generative adversarial networks (GANs) to create high-quality synthetic data to increase the performance of grasp classification.

Clinical Relevance— This approach can increase the decoding performance of already existing decoding algorithms for patients with an amputation and suggests the possibility to increase the protection of personal data when recorded at a larger scale.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromyography (EMG) has been used for decades for the control of commercial robotic prosthetic hands (RPHs) [1]. However, patients were able to control only one degree of freedom (DoF) at the time with non-homologous muscle activity. Patients could cycle between different types of grasps using co-contraction of antagonist muscles or a smartphone app. Since a few years, some companies started to provide faster and more intuitive control of RPHs using pattern recognition methods that allow the patients to perform the intended grasp directly in a homologous way. This method is based on the extraction of discriminative features of the EMG signal that are used to train a classifier and identify the grasp intended by the patient. In the research literature, this approach showed high performance with accuracies up to 95% accuracy on 15 classes [2].

In 2012, deep learning revolutionized the field of image classification in the ImageNET competition beating by more than 10% all the competitors who used a standard approach with feature extraction [3]. Therefore, researchers applied similar approaches to EMG signals and showed an increase in decoding performance [4]. One of the main limitations of deep learning is the amount of data necessary to outperform standard approaches, for instance, the ImageNet dataset has more than 14M images. However, datasets with hours of patient recordings are not feasible due to sweat that changes electrode impedance and muscle fatigue. Such a dataset cannot be recorded over several days due to subject variability among recordings as well as electrode placement which is crucial for comparable recordings [5].

To tackle this issue, several groups showed the possibility to use transfer learning leveraging data acquired from several subjects to create a model that learns a general mapping of EMG signals which is then fine-tuned with a few repetitions of movements performed by the target subject. For instance, Fan et al. [6] showed an increase in decoding accuracy using transfer learning from a database of healthy subjects to patients with an amputation

Another approach is to augment the dataset with synthetic data. Indeed, the combination of deep learning with data augmentation could increase decoding performances. For EMG signals, several techniques exist to increase the diversity of available data such as Gaussian noise addition, magnitude wrapping, wavelet decomposition or synthetic EMG models and can effectively improve decoding performance [7]. To draw a parallel with images, such techniques could be seen as equivalent to classical image data augmentation techniques such as noise addition, flipping, rotation or contrast modification [8]. On the other hand, deep learning approaches with generative adversarial networks (GANs) are capable of generating completely new synthetic images such as faces with different emotions to increase classification accuracy on underrepresented classes [9]. However, despite the promising results with images, deep learning has not been widely investigated for EMG data augmentation. Only a few groups showed the possibility of improving classification accuracy with deep learning approaches. Bird et al. [10] showed a generative algorithm for EEG and EMG data using GPT-2, a transformer-based generator originally developed for text generation. They show a real-time increase in performance with EMG for a three-class decoding task. Campbell et al. [11] used a sinGAN and improved the classification of a six-class decoding task by creating several models for each repetition of each motion per subject. We focused on the model developed by Zanini et al. [12] for Parkinson’s disease EMG data augmentation. The model is a deep convolutional GAN with an architecture that has been modified to capture more relevant features from EMG datasets. The discriminant model consists of four parallel convolutional pipelines that take as input the raw EMG signal, its frequency spectrum using FFT, FFT of the signal envelope as well as wavelet expansion that can extract essential features from EMG signals to perform movement classification.

Another important point has to be taken into consideration. While EMG was mainly used for RPHs, clinicians for diagnostic purposes or research for different robotic applications [1], [12], with the improvement of decoding algorithms and power of embedded electronics, companies

*Research supported by the Swiss National Competence Center for Research in Robotics, the Bertarelli foundation and CHRONOS project funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation. The first two authors contributed equally to this work.

V.M and S.M are with the Bertarelli Foundation Chair in Translational Neuroengineering, Centre for Neuroprosthetics and Institute of

Bioengineering, School of Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland (Corresponding author: silvestro.micera@epfl.ch)

C. L. is pursuing his master degree at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

nowadays consider EMG as a potential interface to interact with computers for games, keyboard typing that could be used by the general public. Personal data anonymization is a key aspect of research and medical environments and should be preserved when such technologies will hit the market. One application of GANs could be the anonymization of biometric data to allow data sharing [13].

In this work, using the same model architecture as in [12], we train a deep convolutional GAN on a simple grasp classification dataset as a first step to create high-quality synthetic EMG data and augmenting a dataset for grasp classification. We report differences in classification accuracy with the addition of synthetic data as well as a close analysis of the amount of generated data necessary. We also investigate whether using only generated data is suitable for this task.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. EMG recording and pre-processing

EMG signal from one healthy subject (Male, 26 years old) was recorded for this study. Ethical approval was obtained from the cantonal ethical committee of Vaud and the subject signed informed consent. EMG signals were recorded at 2kHz using a Noraxon Delsys system connected to a LabJack data acquisition card to record six bipolar electrode channels placed uniformly around the subject's forearm. During acquisition, the EMG signal is amplified and filtered with a notch filter at 50Hz and a bandpass filter between 15-500Hz. To synchronize EMG signals with hand gestures, the subject was asked to follow a virtual hand performing different finger gestures and hold for five seconds; the sequence of movement was repeated five times. In order to reduce synchronization issues between EMG and kinematics, the first second of each grasp was removed to train the GAN. We focused on three types of movements recruiting different sets of muscles: Power grasp, 2-digit pincer grasp, pinky finger closing and rest. For classification, the three first repetitions were considered as the training set while the fourth repetition was used as the validation set and results are reported on the last repetition which is the test set.

B. Generation of synthetic EMG data

Using the model from [12], trained for each of the 6 channels and each class was evaluated for a total of 24 models trained. Each GAN was trained to generate one second of synthetic data using a sliding window of one second of EMG signal with a moving step of one sample. The GAN models were trained on one, two or three repetitions to detect any change in the quality of the generated samples. When using multiple repetitions of movements that are not continuous in time, the sliding window was computed separately on trials.

The discriminative part of the GAN gave more weight to the frequency domain of the EMG signal than the time domain. Therefore, scaling could be an issue when generating different types of grasps separately, as the different models could not learn their relative range of values. Hence, the synthetic data, once generated, was rescaled in order to obtain the same standard deviation of the train set.

C. Synthetic EMG signal validation

To assess synthetic data quality and to quantify the effect of adding generated data for a grasp classification task, we

chose a set of seven well-explored features: Mean Absolute Value (MAV), Waveform Length: Cumulative length of the EMG waveform over time (WL), Maximum Absolute Value (MaxAV), Standard Deviation (STD), Root Mean Square of the EMG signal (RMS), Zero Crossings: Number of times the signal crosses zero (ZC) and Slope Sign Changes: Number of times that the slope of the EMG signal changes sign (SSC).

These features were computed on windows of 250ms with a moving step of 25ms (225ms overlap) to train a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) for grasp classification. The extracted features of the EMG signal and the generated data were standardized based on the train set.

Three conditions were compared: the baseline where the MLP was trained using EMG signal only, the generated condition where the MLP was trained using only synthetic data and the combined condition where a combination of EMG signal and synthetic data was used for training. In the second and third conditions, different amounts of generated data are compared. Then, the classification accuracies of the three conditions are reported on the test set which consists of true EMG signal only. Each training was performed 10 times and mean accuracy is reported with standard deviation.

The MLP is composed of three layers (7 features input per channel, 350 nodes, 50 nodes, 4 classes output). ReLU activation function was used for the first two layers and SoftMax for the last one. Each MLP was trained with a batch size of 16 samples, with 50 epochs, a step decay with a drop of $\frac{1}{2}$ every 10 epochs with an early stopping if the validation loss did not decrease for more than 13 epochs. The models were trained with a cross-entropy loss (categorical cross-entropy), using an Adam optimizer.

III. RESULTS

The first part of the analysis is performed on one GAN only, therefore on one channel, one class and the whole train set (three repetitions of movements) to assess the quality of the generated signals. Then, the analysis is focused on GANs from the same channel for all classes to assess performance differences with the addition of generated data. The quality of generated data is also compared when trained with one, two or three repetitions of movements. Finally, all GANs are used to train a model for grasp classification with the whole train set.

Due to the non-normality of feature distribution (tested with a Shapiro-Wilk test), a Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the distribution of features of generated data and true data. Out of the 24 GANs trained, only 5 produced a similar distribution for at least one feature. Altogether, out of 168 feature distributions compared (24 GANs*7 features), the null hypothesis could not be rejected for 10 distributions.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the extracted features on EMG signals and synthetic data for all classes. A Mann-Whitney U test was also performed mixing all classes and showed that the distributions of each feature are also different ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, a PCA was performed to visualize the seven features of one EMG channel in 2D for all classes and retained 97% of the variance. Generated data was transformed

with the same covariance matrix and is shown in figure 2 together with the true EMG signal.

Figure 1. Distribution of features extracted from EMG signal (true) and synthetic data (generated) for one channel and all classes with the whole train set.

Regarding the classification task with one EMG channel, as shown in figure 3, the baseline accuracy of the classification task increased from one to two repetitions of movements from 0.56 (std=0.04) to 0.70 (std=0.16) (Welch’s test, $p<0.05$), but not from two to three repetitions (Welch’s test, $p=0.062$). On the other hand, the best classification accuracy obtained with generated data increased when the number of repetitions increased (12000, 1250 and 8000 generated samples respectively, Welch’s test, $p<0.05$). The condition with generated data is higher than baseline when the GAN is trained with three repetitions with an accuracy of 0.76 (Welch’s test, $p<0.05$). With three repetitions, generated data alone has a higher test accuracy than the combined condition (Welch’s test, $p<0.05$).

The combination of EMG signal and synthetic data showed an increase between one and two repetitions and between two and three repetitions (Welch’s test, $p<0.05$). The evolution with respect to the amount of generated data added in the train set is shown in figure 4.

With all the channels, the baseline condition has an average accuracy of 0.93 (See figure 5). Nevertheless, with all channels, the condition with generated data only is not different from baseline (1748 generated samples, Welch’s test, $p=0.248$). However, the combined condition (mean=0.942) with 4400 generated samples is higher than the baseline (Welch’s test, $p<0.05$).

Figure 4. Evolution of the accuracy with respect to the number of samples used during training for the three conditions with (A) one repetition of the movements, (B) two repetitions and (C) the whole train set.

IV. DISCUSSION

This work aimed at generating synthetic data to increase performances on a grasp classification task. As highlighted in figure 2, the generated data distribution is different from the true EMG signals. However, new plausible generated data can add additional variability to the input dataset and increase performance on unseen samples.

Figure 2. Two first components extracted from PCA on the EMG signal of one channel for all classes with the whole train set. Generated data was transformed with the same covariance matrix used for the true EMG signal. For clarity, Gaussian kernel density estimates are shown.

Figure 3. Boxplots of the accuracy obtained for the three conditions with (A) one repetition of the movements, (B) two repetitions and (C) the whole train set. Generated and combined accuracy values are obtained with the optimal amount of generated data.

We show in figure 3 that with enough training data, the combination of true features with the right amount of generated data can increase classification accuracy. While the gain in accuracy with one channel is on average 4.9%, the difference with all channels is relatively smaller (1.1%). This result could have several explanations. Indeed, the baseline

accuracy with all channels is already at 93.5% and the small improvement with generated data could be due to a ceiling effect. The other factor comes from the fact that all GAN models were trained independently for each channel and cannot grasp the relationship between channels when generating new samples.

Therefore, a potential improvement would be to design a new GAN architecture capable of generating several channels at once. Other types of models like RNNs specifically tailored to this application could better catch the time evolution of EMG signals. Moreover, such models could be developed for regression that allows more intuitive control of RPHs [1]. However, there are only a few examples of GANs developed for regression problems [14]. When trained with one channel and three repetitions, the performance of the generated condition is similar to the combined condition and can therefore be used to train a classifier without using any true EMG data. This result suggests that generated synthetic data could be a solution to legal and ethical issues of biometric data privacy and use by companies at large scale [13].

Figure 5. (Left) Evolution of the accuracy with respect to the number of samples used during training for the three conditions with all channels on the whole train set. (Right) Boxplots of the accuracy obtained for the three conditions. Generated and combined accuracy values are obtained with the optimal amount of generated data.

V. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this preliminary work showed the possibility to increase the decoding performance of a simple classification task with a focus on the amount of generated data necessary. For future development, more grasps should be added to have a functionally relevant setup for RPH control. Other model architectures (RNNs) should be investigated especially for the generation of synthetic data for regression tasks. Moreover, this approach can be combined with deep convolutional networks to perform classification and transfer learning since deep networks increase greatly their performances with more data. Finally, the results have to be confirmed with patients with amputation in a long-term analysis to assess robustness to electrode shift, sweat or muscle fatigue which are among the main factors that limit the application of such techniques outside of lab settings.

REFERENCES

[1] V. Mendez, F. Iberite, S. Shokur, and S. Micera, "Current Solutions and Future Trends for Robotic Prosthetic Hands," *https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-control-071020-104336*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 595–627, May 2021.

[2] S. Bhagwat and P. Mukherji, "Electromyogram (EMG) based fingers movement recognition using

sparse filtering of wavelet packet coefficients," *Sadhana - Acad. Proc. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Dec. 2020.

[3] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 25, 2012.

[4] P. Xia, J. Hu, and Y. Peng, "EMG-Based Estimation of Limb Movement Using Deep Learning With Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks," *Artif. Organs*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. E67–E77, May 2018.

[5] A. Ameri, M. A. Akhaee, E. Scheme, and K. Englehart, "A Deep Transfer Learning Approach to Reducing the Effect of Electrode Shift in EMG Pattern Recognition-based Control," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, pp. 1–1, 2019.

[6] J. Fan *et al.*, "Improving sEMG-based motion intention recognition for upper-limb amputees using transfer learning," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, pp. 1–11, Jul. 2021.

[7] P. Tsinganos, B. Cornelis, J. Cornelis, B. Jansen, and A. Skodras, "Data augmentation of surface electromyography for hand gesture recognition," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 17, pp. 1–23, Sep. 2020.

[8] C. Shorten and T. M. Khoshgoftaar, "A survey on Image Data Augmentation for Deep Learning," *J. Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–48, Dec. 2019.

[9] X. Zhu, Y. Liu, J. Li, T. Wan, and Z. Qin, "Emotion Classification with Data Augmentation Using Generative Adversarial Networks," *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. (including Subser. Lect. Notes Artif. Intell. Lect. Notes Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10939 LNAI, pp. 349–360, Jun. 2018.

[10] J. J. Bird, M. Pritchard, A. Fratini, A. Ekart, and D. R. Faria, "Synthetic Biological Signals Machine-Generated by GPT-2 Improve the Classification of EEG and EMG through Data Augmentation," *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 3498–3504, Apr. 2021.

[11] E. Campbell, J. A. D. Cameron, and E. Scheme, "Feasibility of Data-driven EMG Signal Generation using a Deep Generative Model," *Proc. Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. EMBS*, vol. 2020-July, pp. 3755–3758, Jul. 2020.

[12] R. A. Zanini and E. L. Colombini, "Parkinson's disease EMG data augmentation and simulation with DCGANs and style transfer," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 9, May 2020.

[13] J. Yoon, L. N. Drumright, and M. Van Der Schaar, "Anonymization through data synthesis using generative adversarial networks (ADS-GAN)," *IEEE J. Biomed. Heal. Informatics*, vol. 24, no. 8, pp. 2378–2388, Aug. 2020.

[14] M. Rezagholiradeh and M. A. Haidar, "Reg-Gan: Semi-supervised learning based on generative adversarial networks for regression," *ICASSP, IEEE Int. Conf. Acoust. Speech Signal Process. - Proc.*, vol. 2018-April, pp. 2806–2810, Sep. 2018.